

POLYNUCLEAR AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS. PART IV. SYNTHESIS
OF SOME 4-METHYL-1:2-BENZANTHRACENE DERIVATIVES

By R. P. GANDHI, K. CHANDER, O. P. VIG AND S. M. MUKHERJI

The method of Mukherji for the synthesis of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons has been extended to the elegant synthesis of 1':4-dimethyl-, 2':4-dimethyl-, 3':4-dimethyl- and 4:5:8-trimethyl-1:2-benzanthracenes.

Schmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1938, **B39**, 59; 1938, **42**, 83; 1939, **44**, 194) considered that the distribution of π -electrons in a hydrocarbon might be one of the factors controlling biological activity. A large number of carcinogenic hydrocarbons exhibited a high-electron density area, designated as K-region, and in biologically active hydrocarbons this charge was found to be more than $1.293e$, introduction of substituents like methyl group enhancing the electron density (Pullman and Pullman, *Rev. Sci.*, 1946, **84**, 154; Dandel, *ibid.*, 1946, **84**, 37). Robinson (*Brit. Med. J.*, 1946, **1**, 943) associated the K-region with the 9:10-double bond in phenanthrene moiety, activated by substituents. But Pullmann *et al.* (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1954, 1097; *Compt. rend.*, 1954, **238**, 964, 1935) have recently modified their earlier views on the minimum energetic index essential for carcinogenicity. They adumbrate, in addition to a favourable K-region, also an L-region. The former is postulated to be permissive or selective and the latter, exclusive. Woernly (*Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1954, **50**, 199), however, regards the carcinogenic character as a result of overall electronic configuration rather than that of a specific region, although the latter may be one of the contributing factors.

However, these speculations regarding structural requirements in relation to carcinogenicity require more substantiation by semi-empirical quest. As a part of the programme of work in this direction, we have synthesised 1':4-dimethyl-, 2':4-dimethyl-, 3':4-dimethyl- and 4:5:8-trimethyl-1:2-benzanthracenes, which are all derivatives of 4-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene. In Part I (this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 697) a very pliant method was described for the synthesis of 4-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene. In view of the fact that this compound is highly carcinogenic whereas the parent compound, 1:2-benzanthracene, is inactive, special importance attaches to our method for the fact that it leads directly to the 4-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene system.

2-Formyl-6-methylcyclohexanone was allylated and then hydrolysed, following essentially the conditions laid down by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 1202) for the preparation of 2-allylcyclohexanone, when 2-allyl-6-methylcyclohexanone was obtained in 54% overall yield. This was then subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with tetralin (Part I, *loc. cit.*) to furnish (IIa) in 48% yield. The ketone (IIa) was reduced (Ponndorf) and the resulting alcohol (IIIa) was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid to (IVa) which was dehydrogenated with 30% palladised charcoal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1130) to 1':4-dimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIa) in 37% overall yield. No other isomeric aromatic products could be detected.

was composed preponderantly of the *cyclohexane* structure (IVc) or of the spiran (Vc=Va). To throw light on this point, which would also determine whether cyclisation of (IIIa) proceeded perceptibly to the spiran (Va), we subjected 2-allyl-4-methyl*cyclohexanone* and tetralin to the above sequence of reactions, when 3':4-dimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIc) was obtained in 38% overall yield. The mixed melting points of the aromatic hydrocarbons (VIa) and (VIc) showed considerable depression, indicating thereby that cyclisation of (IIIa) proceeded practically exclusively to the *cyclohexane* structure (IVa) and not the spiran (Va).

The possibility of cyclisation of (IIIa), (IIIb), (IIIc) and (IIId) in the alternative direction at the position-5 in the tetralin moiety was ruled out on the basis of analogy with our synthesis of 4-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene and 1:4-dimethylanthracene (see Part I, *loc. cit.*). Also, partial cyclisation at position-5 would lead, through the above sequence of reactions, to some 1:4'-dimethyl-, 1:3'-dimethyl-, 1:2'-dimethyl- and 1:5:8-trimethyl-3:4-benzphenanthrene, which, however, could not be detected in the final aromatised products.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Allyl-2-formyl-6-methylcyclohexanone.—To an ice-cooled suspension of sodium ethoxide in benzene (prepared from 3.3 g. of pulverised sodium, 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 200 c.c. of dry benzene) was added dropwise with shaking 2-formyl-6-methyl*cyclohexanone* (20 g.) (prepared in 65% yield from 2-methyl*cyclohexanone* as in the case of 2-formyl-4-methyl*cyclohexanone*, *vide infra*) and kept overnight, when the sodio-salt separated as an orange solid. The mass was cooled and allyl iodide (26 g.) added with shaking. After standing for an hour, the reaction mixture was refluxed on the steam-bath for 8 hours, when the supernatant layer gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The mixture was treated with water and the benzene layer separated, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent the desired product (16 g., 62.2%) came over at 90-95°/7 mm. (Found: C, 73.21; H, 8.57. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.33; H, 8.88%).

2-Allyl-6-methylcyclohexanone.—The above formyl derivative (15 g.) was stirred for 4 hours at 50-55° with 5% KOH solution (150 c.c.). The hydrolysate was acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil.) and the organic product taken up in ether; the ethereal layer was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue, left after removal of the solvent, distilled at 82-85°/7 mm, yield 11 g. (86.8%). (Found: C, 78.68; H, 10.41. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.90; H, 10.52%).

2-[\beta-Methyl-\beta-(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-6-methylcyclohexanone (IIa).—To freshly distilled tetralin (100 c.c.), ice-cooled in a 250 c.c. three-necked flask, fitted with a guard tube, a mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel, was added anhydrous AlCl_3 (17.5 g., 1M) in eight lots in 80 minutes. After the addition of each lot of AlCl_3 , about 1 g. of 2-allyl-6-methyl*cyclohexanone* was added (10 g. in all, 2M). The temperature was not allowed to rise above 5° during the addition. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hours at 0°-5° and then decomposed by ice-cold HCl and the product extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed free of acid and dried (Na_2SO_4)

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

The solvent was removed and the residue on fractionation gave 9 g. (48%) of (IIa), b.p. 200-205°/5 mm. (Found: C, 84.15; H, 10.25. $C_{20}H_{28}O$ requires C, 84.50; H, 9.86%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-6-methylcyclohexanol (IIIa).—The ketone (IIa: 7 g.) in isopropyl alcohol (40 c.c.) was reduced with aluminium isopropoxide (from 2.5 g. Al) and worked up in the usual manner. Distillation of the product furnished 6 g. (85%) of (IIIa) as a colorless viscous oil, b.p. 212-15°/6 mm. (Found: C, 83.44; H, 10.91. $C_{20}H_{28}O$ requires C, 83.91; H, 10.49%).

1':4-Dimethyl-dodecahydro-1:2-benzanthracene (IVa).—The alcohol (IIIa: 5 g.) was treated with H_2SO_4 (7 c.c., d 1.84) in the cold (0°-5°) when 3 g. (64%) of the dodecahydro derivative (IVa) was obtained, b.p. 177-80°/3 mm. (Found: C, 89.83; H, 10.29. $C_{20}H_{28}$ requires C, 89.55; H, 10.45%).

1':4-Dimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIa).—The above product (IVa: 2 g.) was heated with palladised charcoal (30%, 0.2 g.) for 4 hours at 300°-320°. The product was extracted with ether and the solvent removed. The residue was converted into its picrate which was purified by crystallisation from ethanol. The hydrocarbon (VIa) was regenerated from the purified picrate by treatment with dilute ammonia and was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture to obtain 1.3 g. (68%) of (VIa), m.p. 161°. (Found: C, 94.12; H, 6.67. $C_{20}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The picrate obtained as orange-red needles was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 147°. (Found: N, 8.30. $C_{26}H_{18}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.66%).

2-Allyl-5-methylcyclohexanone.—To sodamide prepared *in situ* (Vaughn *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2120) from 4 g. of sodium was added dry benzene (100 c.c.). 3-Methylcyclohexanone (20 g.) was then added dropwise to the well-stirred suspension of sodamide at 5°-10°. The mixture was stirred for 1 hour at room temperature (20°) and then heated on the steam-bath for a further period of 3 hours. It was then cooled at 0°-5° and allyl iodide (32 g.) was added dropwise. After standing for an hour the reaction mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 8 hours. It was then cooled and decomposed and the aqueous portion extracted with ether. The combined extract was then washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removing the solvent, the product (14 g., 51.6%), distilling at 85°-90°/5mm, was collected. The ketone was characterised by its orange 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from ethyl acetate-ethanol mixture, m.p. 132-33°. (Found: N, 16.55. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2N_4$ requires N, 16.86%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-5-methylcyclohexanone (IIb).—2-Allyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (12 g.) was subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with tetralin (120 c.c.) in the presence of finely powdered $AlCl_3$ (21.4 g.) according to the conditions laid down for the preparation (IIa), when 11 g. (49%) of the ketone (IIb), boiling at 205-208°/4mm, was obtained. (Found: C, 84.15; H, 10.46. $C_{20}H_{28}O$ requires C, 84.50; H, 9.86%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-5-methylcyclohexanol (IIIb).—The ketone (IIb: 7 g.) in isopropyl alcohol (35 c.c.) was reduced with aluminium isopropoxide (from 2.5 g. Al) in the usual manner, when 6 g. (85%) of (IIIb) was obtained boiling at 200-202°/4mm. (Found: C, 84.12; H, 10.48. $C_{20}H_{28}O$ requires C, 83.91; H, 10.49%)

2':4-Dimethyl-dodecahydro-1:2-benzanthracene (IVb).—The above alcohol (IIIb: 4 g.) was cyclised with H_2SO_4 (4 c.c., *d* 1.84) as in the case of (IIIa), when 2.5 g. (66.6%) of (IVb) came over at 182-85°/5 mm. (Found: C, 89.92; H, 10.36. $C_{20}H_{28}$ requires C, 89.55; H, 10.45%).

2':4-Dimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIb).—The product (IVb: 1.5 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% palladised charcoal (0.15 g.) at 300°-320° for 4 hours. After working up in the usual way, the dehydrogenated product was converted into its picrate and the picrate, purified by crystallisation from ethanol, was decomposed with dilute ammonia. The regenerated hydrocarbon (VIb) was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture in colorless needles, m.p. 181°, yield 1 g. (70%). (Found: C, 93.30; H, 6.52. $C_{20}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The picrate of (VIb) was crystallised from ethanol as orange-red needles, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: N, 8.45. $C_{24}H_{18}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.66%).

2-Allyl-2-formyl-4-methylcyclohexanone.—To a cooled suspension of sodium ethoxide (from 7 g. of sodium) in benzene (200 c.c.) was added ethyl formate (30 g.). After standing for 2 hours, 4-methylcyclohexanone (23 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.) was added with shaking; a yellow solid mass gradually separated. The mixture was allowed to stand for 6 hours after which it was decomposed with ice-water. The aqueous layer was acidified with ice-cold HCl, when an oil was obtained. On working up in the usual way, 17 g. (60%) of 2-formyl-4-methylcyclohexanone was obtained showing an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, b.p. 90°/5 mm.

The above formyl derivative (16 g.) was added in the cold to a solution of potassium (4.5 g.) in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (200 c.c.) and left overnight when potassium salt separated. To this solid mass was added, with ice-cooling, allyl iodide (22 g.), and the mixture after standing for an hour was refluxed on the steam-bath for 8 hours when it failed to exhibit any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and extracted with benzene. After working in the usual way, 14.5 g. (70%) of 2-allyl-2-formyl-4-methylcyclohexanone was obtained as a clear liquid, b.p. 110-15°/5 mm. (Found: C, 73.06; H, 8.72. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.33; H, 8.88%).

2-Allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone.—The above formyl derivative (14 g.) was mechanically stirred for 4 hours with a 5% KOH solution (150 c.c.) at 50°-55°. It was then cooled and decomposed with iced HCl. After working up in the usual way, 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone (10.5 g., 88%) was obtained as a mobile liquid, b.p. 95-98°/8 mm. (Found: C, 78.42; H, 10.89. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.90; H, 10.52%)

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared by the sulphuric acid method, was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 85°. (Found: N, 16.70. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 16.86%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-4-methylcyclohexanone (IIc).—2-Allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone (10 g.) was treated with tetralin (100 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (18 g.), following the same conditions described in the case of (IIa), when 15 g. (80%) of (IIc) was obtained, b.p. 195-200°/5 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5672. (Found: C, 84.99; H, 9.40. $C_{28}H_{38}O$ requires C, 84.50; H 9.86%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-4-methylcyclohexanol (IIIc).—The above ketone (IIc: 7 g.) was reduced with aluminium isopropoxide (prepared from 2.5 g. of Al),

in the same way as in (IIa), when 6 g. (85%) of the carbinol (IIIc) was obtained, b.p. 209-12°/5 mm., η_D^{25} 1.5630. (Found: C, 84.25; H, 9.98. $C_{20}H_{30}O$ requires C, 83.91; H, 10.49%).

3':4-Dimethyl-dodecahydro-1:2-benzanthracene (IVc).—The above carbinol (5 g.) was stirred with H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 c.c.) in the cold (0°) for 4 hours when 3.8 g. (80%) of the dodecahydro derivative (IVc) was obtained, b.p. 175-77°/3 mm., η_D^{25} 1.5712. (Found: C, 89.99; H, 10.02. $C_{20}H_{28}$ requires C, 89.55; H, 10.45%).

3':4-Dimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIc).—The dodecahydro derivative (IVc: 2 g.) was heated with 30% palladium-charcoal (0.2 g.) at 300°-320° for 4 hours. After working up in the usual manner, 1.4 g. of the aromatised product (VIc) was obtained which was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture as light yellow flakes, m.p. 145-46°; mixed m.p. with (VIa), 135-38°. (Found: C, 93.71; H, 6.29. $C_{20}H_{14}$ requires C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The picrate, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 179-80° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{26}H_{19}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.66%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(1':4'-dimethyl-6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-cyclohexanone (IIId)—2-Allylcyclohexanone (Mukherji and Bhattacharyya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202) (15 g.) was subjected to cationoid reaction with 1:4-dimethyltetralin (I: $R_1 = R_2 = Me$) (*idem*, *Science & Culture*, 1951, 16, 374) (35 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (26.8 g.), following the conditions as described for the preparation of (IIa), when 12 g. (36.5%) of the ketone (IIId) was obtained, b.p. 200-205°/2mm. (Found: C, 84.87; H, 10.39. $C_{21}H_{30}O$ requires C, 84.51; H, 10.13%).

2-[β -Methyl- β -(1':4'-dimethyl-6'-tetralyl)-ethyl]-cyclohexanol (IIIId).—The above ketone (IIId: 7 g.) was reduced with aluminium isopropoxide (from 2.5 g. Al in 50 c.c. isopropyl alcohol) in the usual way, when 5 g. (83%) of the alcohol (IIIId) was obtained as a colorless viscous oil, b.p. 210-15°/6 mm. (Found: C, 83.47; H, 10.26. $C_{21}H_{32}O$ requires C, 83.94; H, 10.73%).

4:5:8-Trimethyl-dodecahydro-1:2-benzanthracene (IVd).—The carbinol (IIIId: 4 g.) was cyclised by the action of H_2SO_4 (4 c.c., d 1.84) as in the case of (IIIa), when 2.4 g. (63.7%) of the cyclised product (IVd) was obtained, b.p. 175-78°/5 mm. (Found: C, 89.71; H, 10.33. $C_{21}H_{30}$ requires C, 89.29; H, 10.71%).

4:5:8-Trimethyl-1:2-benzanthracene (VIId).—The cyclised product (IVd: 2 g.) was dehydrogenated with 0.2 g. of 30% palladised charcoal at 300°-320° for 4 hours as in the case of (IVa). The hydrogenated product obtained after the usual working up was converted into its picrate which was purified through crystallisation from ethanol as dark red needles, m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 8.45. $C_{27}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 8.41%). The purified picrate was then decomposed with dilute ammonia and the regenerated hydrocarbon (VIId) was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture to furnish 1.4 g. (73.7%) of the pure hydrocarbon (VIId), m.p. 74-75°. (Found: C, 93.66; H, 6.52. $C_{21}H_{14}$ requires C, 93.29; H, 6.71%).